

sulphate, hydrazine dihydrochloride, N-N-diphenyl hydrazine and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone was 5, 7, 4, 6 and 6 mol respectively.

The recommended procedure was applied for the determination of phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride, semicarbazide, hydrazine sulphate, hydrazine dihydrochloride, N-N'-diphenyl hydrazine and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone derivatives. Amounts ranging from 1, 2 and 3 mg were taken and three experiments were performed for each sample size. The average % error reported for phenylhydrazine hydrochloride was ± 0.45 , semicarbazide ± 0.33 , hydrazine sulphate ± 0.54 , hydrazine dihydrochloride ± 0.69 , N-N-diphenyl hydrazine ± 0.59 , and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone ± 0.79 . On the whole the deviation of the results is within 1%.

Considering the oxidation reaction of hydrazine derivatives and the number of equivalents of Ce(IV) consumed for a particular sample, the following course of reactions (Fig. 1) may be suggested for the oxidation of hydrazine derivatives.

Fig. 1. Proposed course of reaction for the oxidation of hydrazine derivatives.

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Effect of Electrolytes on the Creaming and Demulsification of O/W Emulsions Stabilized by Soaps

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A survey of literature reveals that oil/water emulsions have been prepared by employing soaps¹, protein+soaps², saponin+soaps³, resin soaps⁴ and metal soaps⁵ as emulsifiers. Their properties such as surface tension⁶, viscosity³, creaming⁷, aging⁷ etc have been studied. But the authors have introduced 2-pyridine ethanol sod. oleate as new soap and have studied its physical properties⁸. After studying the physical properties of oil/water emulsions⁹ stabilized by 2-pyridine ethanol sod. oleate, it was thought worthwhile to present a systematic data of creaming and demulsification concentration of different electrolytes for these emulsions.

Experimental

Double distilled kerosene (sp. gr. 0.7948 g/ml), turpentine (sp. gr. 0.8745 g/ml) and water having conductance $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were used in all the experiments. All the electrolytes used were of BDH, AR grade. 2-Pyridine ethanol sodium oleate has been prepared by refluxing 2-pyridine ethanol, oleic acid and NaOH in equimolar ratio⁹.

Preparation of emulsions : O/W emulsions have been prepared by taking kerosene, turpentine and mixed oil (50% kerosene+50% turpentine) as internal phase and water as external phase in the ratio of 1 : 3 and soap concentration was kept 1% constant by agent-in-water method⁹.

Five test-tubes were taken and labeled 1,2,3,4,5 and 5 ml of N/10 solution of the electrolytes investigated were added to tubes 1,2,3,4 and 5 respectively and the total volume made to 5 ml by adding suitable volumes of conductivity water. To each of the mixture 5 ml of emulsions was added and kept undisturbed for 6 hrs. Two concentrations of electrolytes have been experimentally determined ; (i) the concentration at which the emulsion is separated into a dilute emulsion layer and thick or viscous creamed layer and (ii) the concentration at which the emulsion is separated into a aqueous

NOTES

TABLE 1(a)—EFFECT OF ELECTROLYTES ON THE CREAMING AND BREAKING OF THE OIL/WATER EMULSIONS

Name of electrolyte	Temp. 25°		2-Pyridine Ethanol Sod. Oleate Concentration : 1%			
	kerosene/water		turpentine/water		mixed oil/water	
	creaming × M	breaking × M	creaming × M	breaking × M	creaming × M	breaking × M
KCl	0.055	0.066	0.056	0.068	0.057	0.069
KBr	0.034	0.040	0.035	0.042	0.036	0.043
KI	0.051	0.035	0.032	0.036	0.033	0.037
K ₂ CrO ₄	0.020	0.025	0.023	0.026	0.025	0.035
KNO ₃	0.025	0.030	0.028	0.031	0.030	0.033
KMnO ₄	0.010	0.015	0.012	0.017	0.014	0.019

TABLE 1(b)

Name of electrolyte	kerosene/water		turpentine/water		mixed oil/water	
	creaming × M	breaking × M	creaming × M	breaking × M	creaming × M	breaking × M
	KCl	0.055	0.066	0.056	0.068	0.057
CaCl ₂	0.012	0.015	0.013	0.016	0.017	0.018
AlCl ₃	0.009	0.010	0.0092	0.011	0.0095	0.013
SnCl ₄	0.0081	0.0092	0.0084	0.0095	0.0086	0.0097

TABLE 1(c)

Name of electrolyte	kerosene/water		turpentine/water		mixed oil/water	
	creaming × M	breaking × M	creaming × M	breaking × M	creaming × M	breaking × M
	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.061	0.064	0.062	0.068	0.063
Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄	0.054	0.060	0.057	0.062	0.058	0.063
Ba(OAc) ₂	0.042	0.044	0.045	0.048	0.047	0.049
NH ₄ SCN	0.030	0.035	0.032	0.036	0.035	0.038

phase layer and clear oil layer. The results are summarised in Tables 1(a), 1(b) and 1(c). All the experiments were carried out at 25°.

Results and Discussion

The data presented in Tables 1(a), 1(b) and 1(c) indicate that creaming and demulsification concentration depend markedly on the valency and size of counter ion present in the added electrolyte. The electrolytes may act as follows :

(i) After the preparation of emulsion, it may contain oil droplets of different sizes and some of them may be very small. So these droplets cream very slowly, but the addition of electrolytes, affect the stability¹⁰ of these droplets and cause their flocculation to some extent and thus increase the rate of creaming, while at higher concentration the droplets coalesce with each other and result in the breaking of the emulsions.

(ii) When the droplets move upward, the diffuse part of the electrical double layer surrounding each droplet of oil is distorted and addition of electrolyte lowers the potential of diffuse double layer and also the "sedimentation potential" and thus increases the rate of creaming and finally breaks the emulsions.

It is concluded from the data that as the valency of ion increases they become more effective and less concentration is required to creaming and breaking of emulsions. The order being Sn⁴⁺ < Al³⁺ < Ca²⁺ < K⁺, while in case of anions the order is MnO₄⁻ < CrO₄²⁻

< NO₃⁻ < I⁻ < Br⁻ < Cl⁻. So now it is clear that smaller the size of cation and greater the size of anion is more effective. Table 1(c) shows that NH₄SCN is more effective than that of Ba(OAc)₂, Na₂C₂O₄ and Na₂SO₄.

It is also concluded from the above observations that nature of the oil phase also plays an important role in the creaming and breaking of emulsions. It is clear that kerosene/water emulsions required less amount of electrolytes for creaming and breaking, while mixed oil/water emulsions required highest amount.

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